

Metrological evaluation of contactless sleep position recognition using an accelerometric smart bed and machine learning

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ABSTRACT

Precise categorization of sleep postures is essential for evaluating overall physical and mental condition. A smart bed was constructed with the microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) accelerometer sensor and an STM 32-bit microcontroller board. This work applies machine learning (ML) methods to acceleration data to accurately categorize four main sleep positions: right side, left side, prone, and supine without any wearable devices. In this work, the efficiency of 9 ML methods is examined. These algorithms include Logistic Regression (LR) with one-vs-rest and multinomial logistic regression types, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), K-Nearest Neighbors Classification (KNN), Classification and Regression Trees (CART), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machines (SVMs) with one-vs-one and one-vs-rest types, and Random Forest (RF). The best hyperparameters of each model was accomplished, based on GridSearchCV. The K-fold cross-validation with the assessing measurement stability results indicate that the LG-OvR, LDA, and RF models have the best performance, whereas LG-OvR model possesses accuracy rates of almost 99%. Furthermore, precision, recall and F1-score are calculated with minimum value of 0.95 for all chosen models. The training and test time are also presented for the selected models. This research has important implications for healthcare, sports medicine, and ergonomics, demonstrating the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches in improving sleep monitoring methods.

1. Introduction

Gaining insight into sleep patterns and positions is crucial for evaluating one's general health and well-being. The correct sleep position is not only crucial for getting a good night's sleep, but it is also essential for reducing many health issues. Studies indicate that various sleep positions can affect how we breathe, our spine's alignment, and our overall comfort while sleeping [1–4]. As a result, these postures can impact our physiological processes and overall health [5]. Individuals with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) [6,7] frequently display postural preferences that can worsen their disease. Identifying and tracking these

preferences can assist in the control of OSA and provide valuable information for individualized treatment strategies. Likewise, particular sleep positions may be required to alleviate symptoms and ensure ideal comfort for medical disorders such as acid reflux, discomfort associated to pregnancy, and musculoskeletal concerns. Sleep posture detection is essential in clinical settings and relevant in sports medicine and rehabilitation [8,9]. Athletes who are recuperating from injuries or engaging in training programs may find it advantageous to observe their sleep positions in order to enhance their recovery and performance. Furthermore, evaluating sleep position can offer helpful knowledge regarding ergonomic design principles for bedding and furniture, aiding

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in developing sleep settings that promote health and well-being.

Wearable devices are popular tools to acquire motion data that have been commonly used for posture detection. In article [10], a wearable sleeping-position monitoring device uses resistive strain gauges sensor attached to the subject's left, right lateral lumbar, upper and lower spine, by a muscle patch, to measure the dynamic changes in the subject's sleeping position, and the six-axis motion sensor in the waist pack for

monitoring the turning movement. Moreover, Machine Learning [11–13], a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is able to analyse the collected data and optimize the algorithm to recognize the sleeping position [14]. ML extracts relevant features from the collected data, such as body orientation, pressure distribution, or movement patterns. Then, the model learns to map the input features to the corresponding sleeping positions. A work in [15] designed a platform integrating a triaxial accelerometer in a wearable device placed on the neck. Two ML algorithms were applied to classify the sleep posture from the accelerations. Another research [16] proposes a wearable sleep position tracking system consisting of two wristbands and one chest band with spatial state classification like Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Random Forest (RF).

Although these wearable approaches have achieved certain of success in sleep posture classification, there are some issues with this method. Various electronic devices intended for sleep tracking might cause discomfort, particularly when used for extended durations. Wearable devices placed on the wrist, head, or chest might cause irritation, create pressure points, or limit movement when sleeping, resulting in discomfort and potentially affecting sleep quality. Furthermore, wearing wearable gadgets before sleep might be uncomfortable and disturb established bedtime patterns. Users may find it inconvenient to consistently remember to wear the device every night, mainly if it necessitates charging or synchronization with a smartphone application. Compatibility concerns are also a cause for concern. Certain users may have compatibility concerns with wearable devices, especially if they have sensitivities to specific materials or if their device lacks the ability to suit various body types or sizes. This feature can further contribute to discomfort and reduce the device's effectiveness for sleep tracking.

There are some Deep Learning (DL) techniques which does not require the wearable tools. The DL method [17] applied to the pressure sensor data. The pre-processed pressure data were fed into a deep model for feature extraction and classification. In paper [18], another system also uses heat map from a pressure sensing mat with piezo-resistive material to be placed on a mattress. Then, a convolution neural network (CNN) is used to recognize different sleeping postures.

Heat map images generated from pressure readings for sleep posture detection have some disadvantages despite their usefulness in visualizing sleep patterns. Heat maps generated from pressure readings may lack sufficient resolution to accurately capture subtle variations in sleep posture. This point can result in the oversimplification of sleep positions, potentially missing important details about sleep behaviour. Heat maps/pressure maps are based on pressure readings from sensors embedded in the sleep surface, such as a mattress or sleep tracker. However, these sensors may not capture all movements accurately, leading to gaps or inaccuracies in the data reflected in the heat map. Furthermore, high-quality pressure sensors capable of generating accurate heat maps can be expensive, potentially limiting access for some users. Additionally, ongoing costs such as maintenance or replacement of sensors may further deter individuals from adopting this technology.

In this regard, this research constructs a low-cost contactless system that is able to achieve sleep posture recognition with the acceleration sensor mounted under a smart bed. The time-series acceleration sensor data is grouped as temporal windows. Each window contain 125 samples. Subsequently 42 input features are computed from the windows to be fed into the proposed ML models. The K-fold cross-validation technique is used to compare the accuracy of 9 candidate models. The three best models are passed to the next round, where further analysis is

applied, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

With the advent of MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems) accelerometers, a promising avenue for non-intrusive monitoring of sleep positions emerges. This technology is integrated with ML algorithms, offering a sophisticated approach to accurately classify sleep positions and providing valuable insights for healthcare professionals and individuals. This work focuses on the utilization of 9 ML algorithms to categorize four main sleep positions: right side, left side, prone, and supine. The comparison between the effectiveness of each model is carried out in this specific case. The examined algorithms are Logistic Regression (LR) [19] with one-vs-rest (OvR) [20] and multinomial logistic regression [21], Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) [22–24], K-Nearest Neighbors Classification (KNN) [25,26], Classification and Regression Trees (CART) [27,28], Naive Bayes (NB) [29,30], Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [31] with one-vs-one (OvO) [32] and one-vs-rest (OvR) [33] strategies, and Random Forest (RF) [34–36]. The hyperparameters of each model is optimized to reach their best potential. The main goal is to determine the most appropriate ML system for accurately categorizing sleep positions using accelerometer data. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of each algorithm, we utilize standard metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. In addition, we provide thorough analyses, which include confusion matrices, to clarify the classification outcomes and identify the differences between the expected and actual labels.

The main achievements, including contributions, can be summarized as follows:

1. The low-cost smart bed system was constructed to monitor the users in a contactless manner without wearable devices to guarantee comfort.
2. Diverse feature selection from accelerometer data to achieve sleep posture recognition with ML models can be adopted by other researchers who work in the field.
3. Deep analysis and examination of robust ML algorithms demonstrate the high potential capability of AI applications in healthcare.
4. Results of this study reveal that both LG-OvR, LDA, and RF models have outstanding performance and high accuracy rates. The results highlight the capability of ML approaches, especially when combined with MEMS accelerometer data, to reliably determine sleep postures. This study not only advances the field of sleep monitoring but also highlights the effectiveness of ML algorithms in healthcare applications. Our research aims to clarify the best method for classifying sleep positions, which will lead to the development of more effective sleep assessment techniques, ultimately resulting in better health outcomes and a higher quality of life.

The paper is organized as follows: the 1st part depicts the smart bed components and its working principle. The following section is about ML model description and ML feature extraction. Then, the experimental parts contain the accuracy comparison of all concerned models, and the two best models participate in further evaluation of the confusion matrix, precision, recall, and F1-score. The last part is the algorithm execution/training time comparison between selected models and the

Fig. 1. System operation diagram.

Fig. 2. Data acquisition diagram.

conclusion, which summarizes the achievements of the whole research.

2. Setup and devices

The smart bed was installed with a 3-axis MEMS Accelerometer that has a 20-bit resolution for measuring acceleration, as depicted in Fig. 2. The IoT kit STM32 B-L475-IOT01A [37] microcontroller board has obtained acceleration data using serial peripheral interface communication (SPI). The tracks from the accelerometer were promptly transmitted to a workstation for immediate recording in text files. Subsequently, these files were utilized to train and evaluate the ML algorithms created using the Python programming language [38], leveraging its specialized artificial intelligence packages: Scikit-learn [39].

The MEMS accelerometer ADXL355 [40] is enclosed in a protective covering and positioned correctly beneath the bed frame, as illustrated in Fig. 3. It is then linked to the microcontroller’s platform using an SPI connection. The sensor delivers acceleration data in a 32-bit digital format for

the X, Y, and Z axes. The sample rate was set at 250 samples per second. The collected data, including X, Y, Z, and finger pulse, is transferred to the workstation via a serial connection operating at a baud rate of 921,600. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the encapsulated accelerometer and connected microcontroller. All the devices were installed under the bed, as shown in Fig. 5. The main characteristics of the sensor were reported in Table I. ADXL 355 has 20-bit ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter), provides 2^{20} (about 1048,576) levels of resolution, which allows for high precision measurements.

3. Data collection and ML algorithms

3.1. Data collection

*Note: The informed consent was obtained for this project.

The measurements of each individual were obtained in four different laying positions: 1. prone, 2. back, 3. right side, and 4. left side. Each location serves as the reference or ground truth for the related accel-

$$N_{\text{Window}} = \frac{\text{total sample}}{\text{sample per window}} = \frac{\text{sample rate} \times \text{acquisition time} \times \text{position number} \times \text{participant number}}{\text{sample per window}}$$

eration data, which is used to train the machine learning model. The research focused on monitoring individuals during sleep under resting settings without any significant physical exertion prior to or during the test. Before the testing, they refrained from engaging in intense walking or running activities. Instead, they either remained at rest or walked regularly for a minimum of 15 minutes. Accelerations were obtained for a duration of 180 seconds for each position. All the values are converted to absolute values for system.

Hence, each participant has produced 4 files (one for position) with 45,000 lines (180 s with 250 Hz) and 4 columns (X-axis, Y-axis, and Z-axis and lying position) for an overall 40 files of raw data. In the next

Fig. 3. Encapsulated accelerometer under the bed frame.

Fig. 4. STM32 platform for sensor pulse and accelerometer.

phase, raw data were elaborated before being used to train ML algorithms. A bandpass filter digitally filters raw acceleration along the X-axis, Y-axis, and Z-axis at [0.5–20] Hz to remove unnecessary noise and make the signal smoother.

A window of 125 samples is exploited to extract the relevant features. ML model will predict the lying posture after each window of 125 samples. Therefore, there are 14,400 windows for all signals, calculated as follows:

$$= \frac{250 \times 180 \times 4 \times 10}{125} = 14400 \tag{1}$$

where: N_{Window} is the window number.

3.2. ML models

There are nine ML algorithms in the project: Logistic Regression (LR) one-vs-rest (OvR) and multinomial logistic regression, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), K-Nearest Neighbors Classification (KNN),

Fig. 5. Smart bed under testing.

Table I
ADXL 355 characteristics.

Parameters	Utilized Value
Scale Range	±2g
Sensitivity	400 mV/g
Temperature Sensitivity	±0.01%/°C
Noise (Spectral Density)	22.5 µg/√Hz

Classification and Regression Trees (CART), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machines (SVMs) one-vs-one (OvO) or one-vs-rest (OvR), Random Forest (RF).

LR is a statistical method used to model the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It is commonly used to predict binary outcomes or probabilities. Logistic Regression can be expanded to accommodate many classes by employing OvR or multinomial logistic regression approaches. Within the framework of OvR, a distinct binary logistic regression model is developed for each class, considering it as the positive class and the remaining classes as the negative class. Another type of LR is multinomial logistic regression, which involves training a single model to directly predict the probability of each class using a softmax function.

LDA is a statistical technique used to find a linear combination of features that maximally separates two or more data classes. Linear Discriminant Analysis has the inherent ability to deal with many classes effectively. This algorithm utilizes Bayes' theorem to calculate the posterior probability of a sample belonging to each class by modelling the distribution of each class. Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) aims to identify linear combinations of features that effectively distinguish between various classes by increasing the variation between classes and decreasing the variation within each class.

KNN is a machine learning algorithm. K-Nearest Neighbors can classify multi class by employing a majority vote mechanism among the k nearest neighbors. The voting process assigns a vote to each class based on the proportion of its instances among the k neighbors. The projected class is determined by selecting the class with the most votes.

CART are a type of algorithm used for both classification and regression tasks. The CART algorithm is capable of doing multi-class classification by expanding the decision tree structure to include many branches, each corresponding to a specific class. The CART algorithm selects the split at each node based on the criterion that maximizes class purity or information gain, taking into account all classes.

NB is inherently capable of handling classification problems with numerous classes. The algorithm uses Bayes' theorem and assumes feature independence to compute the probability of each class based on the input features.

SVM is a type of machine learning algorithm. SVM has the capability

to do classification tasks involving several classes by employing either the OvO or OvR techniques. Within the OvO framework, SVM creates a separate binary classifier for every pair of classes. Predictions are then made by aggregating the votes from all the classifiers. Within the framework of OvR, SVM builds a separate binary classifier for each class compared to all other classes. The class with the most significant confidence score is then chosen.

RF is inherently capable of effectively handling classification problems involving numerous classes. The algorithm builds a collection of decision trees throughout the training process and combines their predictions using voting or average methods to generate the final forecasts for each class.

4. ML features for sleep position recognition

As reported in Table II, there are 42 input features for ML system operation. These input features are obtained as follows:

- Xsum_bool, Ysum_bool, Zsum_bool are the Boolean value of each window sum, respect to the mean of all window sum along each axis.

$$M_W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_W} W_i}{n_W} \tag{2}$$

Where: n_W is the total window number; W_i is the sum of all acceleration samples per each window; M_W is the mean of all window sum.

In each window:

$$\text{If } W_i \geq M_W \rightarrow \text{sum_bool} = 1.$$

Table II
ML input features.

Input Features			Sleep Position
1.Xsum_bool	15.Ysum_bool	29.Zsum_bool	1.Right side
2.Xcounter_bool	16.Ycounter_bool	30.Zcounter_bool	2.Left side
3.Xsum	17.Ysum	31.Zsum	3.Prone
4.Xstd	18.Ystd	32.Zstd	4.Supine
5.Xcounter	19.Ycounter	33.Zcounter	
6.Xmax	20.Ymax	34.Zmax	
7.Xspikes	21.Yspikes	35.Zspikes	
8.ΔXsum_bool	22.ΔYsum_bool	36.ΔZsum_bool	
9.ΔXcounter_bool	23.ΔYcounter_bool	37.ΔZcounter_bool	
10.ΔXsum	24.ΔYsum	38.ΔZsum	
11.ΔXstd	25.ΔYstd	39.ΔZstd	
12.ΔXcounter	26.ΔYcounter	40.ΔZcounter	
13.ΔXmax	27.ΔYmax	41.ΔZmax	
14.ΔXspikes	28.ΔYspikes	42.ΔZspikes	

If $W_i < M_W \rightarrow \text{sum_bool} = 0$.

- Xcounter_bool, Ycounter_bool and Zcounter_bool are the Boolean value of each time a sample value in the window is greater than the mean of all sample value.

$$M_{acc} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_{acc}} acc_i}{n_{acc}} \quad (3)$$

Where: n_{acc} is the total sample number along each axis; acc is acceleration value along each axis; M_{acc} is the mean of all samples along each axis.

If $acc_i \geq M_{acc} \rightarrow \text{counter} + 1$.

If $acc_i < M_{acc} \rightarrow \text{counter} + 0$.

By this way, each window has a certain counter number, called as counter_window. Mean counter is the average value of the counter value of all windows.

In each window:

If counter_window $> M_{acc} \rightarrow \text{counter_bool} = 1$

If counter_window $< M_{acc} \rightarrow \text{counter_bool} = 0$

- Xsum, Ysum, Zsum are the sum of acceleration along X, Y, Z-axes for each window.
- X_counter, Y counter, Z counter: In each window, each time a sample is greater than the mean value, X counter + 1.
- Xstd, Ystd, Zstd are the standard deviation of acceleration along X, Y, Z-axes for each window.
- Xmax, Y max, Zmax are the maximum value of acceleration along X, Y, Z-axes for each window.
- Number of spikes (Xspikes, Yspikes, Zspikes) are absolute value of each sample in the window which is greater than the threshold.

Where: $\text{threshold} = (\text{acc}_{\max} - \text{acc}_{\min}) * 0.1$ with acc_{\max} and acc_{\min} are the maximum and minimum value of acceleration along X, Y, Z-axes.

The difference between 2 consecutive accelerations (Δacc) are calculated, then proceeding with similar feature characteristics as the above calculations to achieve:

- $\Delta Xsum_bool$, $\Delta Ysum_bool$, $\Delta Zsum_bool$ show whether Δ sum in each window is greater than the Δ sum mean of all windows.
- $\Delta Xcounter_bool$, $\Delta Ycounter_bool$, $\Delta Zcounter_bool$ show whether Δ counter in each window is greater than the Δ counter mean of all windows.
- $\Delta Xsum$, $\Delta Ysum$, $\Delta Zsum$ is the sum of Δacc along each axis for each window.
- $\Delta Xstd$, $\Delta Ystd$, $\Delta Zstd$ is the standard deviation of Δacc along each axis for each window.
- $\Delta Xmax$, $\Delta Ymax$, $\Delta Zmax$ is the maximum value of Δacc along each axis for each window.
- $\Delta X_counter$, $\Delta Y_counter$, $\Delta Z_counter$: sample numbers are greater than the mean of all Δ data along each axis in each window.
- $\Delta Xspikes$, $\Delta Yspikes$, $\Delta Zspikes$ are absolute value of each sample in the window which is greater than the Δ threshold. Where: Δ threshold = $(\Delta max - \Delta min) * 0.1$

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Test and result analysis description

The AI models were trained on the host computer, containing an NVIDIA Quadro P620 with a Pascal GPU with 512 CUDA cores (NVIDIA, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The machine includes 2 GB of GDDR5 memory, an Intel Core i7 vPro-10850H Processor running at 2.70 GHz, and 32 GB of RAM (Intel, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The result analysis part contains 3 main contents:

- The 1st comparison of accuracy is carried out by using K-fold cross-validation, a widely used technique in ML that assesses the efficiency of

a predictive model and minimizes the risk of overfitting. The procedure includes splitting the dataset into K subsets or folds, training, and evaluating the model K times. During each iteration, one specific fold is assigned as the test set, while the rest of the K-1 folds are used for training. The findings are calculated by averaging across K iterations, guaranteeing a more robust and reliable performance estimation. The K-fold cross-validation was performed using a value of K equal to 10.

- In the 2nd test, the total data are shuffled randomly, and 30 % of the data is utilized for the test process. Only the ML models with an accuracy greater or equal to 90 % of accuracy from the previous validation are sufficient to participate in this test. The comparisons will be conducted in terms of confusion matrix, precision, recall and F1-score.
- The last examination is about the time evaluation in both training time and test time for each model from the 2nd test.

5.2. Hyperparameter optimization

To optimize the best hyperparameters of each model, hyperparameter Tuning with GridSearchCV [41] was applied. This method tries all the combinations of the values passed in the dictionary and evaluates the model for each combination using the cross-validation process. After using this function, the accuracy for every combination of hyperparameters are calculated and the one with the best performance is selected as reported in Table III.

5.3. Model comparison and selection

With best hyperparameters, K-cross validation is processed with all

Table III
Hyperparameter information.

Model	Best Hyperparameters
LR-OvR	C parameter controls the regularization strength. Smaller C (Stronger Regularization) encourages smaller coefficients by penalizing large values; reduces the risk of overfitting, making the model simpler; it can result in underfitting if the regularization is too strong. Larger C (Weaker Regularization) allows the model to fit the training data more closely by permitting larger coefficients; increases the risk of overfitting, especially with noisy data C = 1. Solver is liblinear (Library for Large Linear Classification) [42], used for solving linear classification problems, efficient in one-vs-rest classification.
LR-Multinomial	C= 10. Maximum number of iterations is 200 for optimization to converge, which prevents premature termination, ensuring optimal results. Solver: Limited-memory Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno algorithm [43]
LDA	Solver: Singular Value Decomposition for dimensionality reduction without requiring covariance matrix estimation.
KNN	Number of neighbors = 10. A larger number smooths the decision boundary, reducing overfitting. Weighting neighbors by their distance from the query point. Closer neighbors have more influence, improving predictions in dense regions.
CART	Maximum depth of the tree = 30. Minimum samples required = 5 to split a node, preventing splitting on nodes with few samples, reducing overfitting.
NB	No hyperparameter
SVM-Ov0 and SVM-OvR	Regularization parameter (C) = 10; higher values focus on reducing classification error. This parameter allows for tighter decision boundaries and reduces misclassification. Kernel coefficient automatically scaled based on feature variance, adjusting the influence of individual data points, improving decision boundary flexibility.
RF	Maximum depth of each tree = 20, which limits tree growth, balancing model complexity and overfitting. Minimum samples required = 2 to split a node. It allows deep splits for trees, capturing more complex patterns. Number of trees in the forest = 200 increases robustness and reduces variance by aggregating more trees.

Table IV
AI models comparison.

Models	Mean Accuracy	Std
LR-OvR	0.987	0.002
LR-Multinomial	0.849	0.028
LDA	0.978	0.006
KNN	0.453	0.0183
CART	0.907	0.007
NB	0.678	0.011
SVM-Ov0	0.650	0.011
SVM-OvR	0.773	0.012
RF	0.976	0.005

the concerned models. As reported in Table IV and Table V, the LR-OvR accomplishes the highest accuracy with low standard deviation (std), while LDA and RF algorithms also obtain the high-quality performance among other operated models. KNN and SVM have low fit for this circumstance, especially KNN with poor correctness only about 45 % of accuracy. Then, LR-Multinomial and NB have superior results with approximately 84 % AND 67 % of accuracy respectively. Nevertheless, these results are not sufficient to be trusted for long-term operation. On the other hand, CART reach higher accuracy with more than 90 % accuracy, but its efficiency are still inferior to LR-OvR, LDA and RF models as shown in Fig. 6 and Table IV. Therefore, the detailed comparison will concentrate on LR-OvR, LDA, and RF as applied models for lying

Table V
LG-OvR and CART table metric of test data.

Sleep Position	Precision			Recall			F1-score			Support Sample Number
	LG-OvR	LDA	RF	LG-OvR	LDA	RF	LG-OvR	LDA	RF	
Right Side	0.98	0.95	0.94	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.95	1085
Left Side	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.97	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	1078
Prone	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.97	0.95	0.99	0.98	0.96	1116
Supine	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.98	0.96	0.98	0.98	0.97	933
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total Accuracy of LG-OvR model: 98.55 % • Total Accuracy of LDA model: 97.76 % • Total Accuracy of RF model: 96.96 % 									4212

position detection.

5.4. Comparison between LG-OvR model and cart model

A confusion matrix is a table that is used to evaluate the performance of multiple-class classification. It visualizes the performance of the classifier by summarizing the counts of true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN) predictions. Each row represents the instances in the actual class. Each column represents the instances predicted to be in that class. The diagonal elements (from top-left to bottom-right) represent correct predictions, while off-diagonal elements represent misclassifications. Through the examination of the confusion matrix, various performance metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score can be calculated for each class. This analysis offers valuable information about the classifier’s capabilities and limitations across multiple classes.

Precision measures the accuracy of each class predictions by the model, indicating the ratio of true prediction number among all the predictions about that class.

Recall measures the ability of the model to find all the relevant cases within the data, indicating the ratio of true prediction number among true labels.

F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It provides a balance score between precision and recall and is often used as a single

Fig. 6. K-fold cross-validation for model evaluations.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix of LR-OvR, LDA and RF models of test for 4 sleep positions.

metric to evaluate a model’s performance.

Fig. 7 shows the confusion matrix of LR-OvR, LDA and RF for test data. The LR-OvR model shows the highest accuracy with the least misprediction among 3 selected models generally. Compared with LR-OvR, the LDA models have superior result in ‘right-side position prediction, but other 3 position prediction has lower amount of correctness. On the other hand, the RF has the most impressive prediction in left-side position but less precise in supine classification.

Table V reports the high-quality functioning of all 3 models with good evaluation metrics. Their total accuracies are all greater than 96 %, especially LR-OvR achieves almost 99 % of accuracy. Together with precision, recall and F1-score, all 3 models have good capability of sleep-position detection.

5.5. Operating time comparison

Table VI reports each selected model’s training time and test time in milliseconds (ms). The RF occupies the longest time for both the training and test process. Instead of training a single model, RF trains multiple decision trees, which increases computational complexity. Each tree in the forest is trained on a different subset of the data, requiring multiple

Table VI Time comparison between 4 selected models.

ML model	Training Time (ms)	Test Time (ms)
LG-OvR	1090.031	0.965
LDA	80.003	0.998
RF	8099.036	102.963

passes through the dataset. On the other hand, the LDA model executes the training data for the quickest period, but LG-OvR performs faster in test data.

6. Conclusion

This work demonstrates the efficacy of ML algorithms in precisely categorizing sleep positions using data obtained from MEMS accelerometers. After assessing different machine learning algorithms, LR, LDA, KNN, CART, NB, SVM, and RF. Proposed feature selection from accelerometer data are also useful for other researchers to consider in posture recognition based on the accelerometer sensor.

LG-OvR, LDA and RF algorithms were chosen for further analysis with confusion matrix and other ML metrics. The results show that the LG-OvR is the most effective with accuracy rates of over 98 %, with fastest execution time after training period. LDA is also competitive model in term of precision and requires least training time. Meanwhile, RF consumes more time of training and test considerably. Taking into account both in terms of time and performance, the LDA is the most suitable algorithm for this specific circumstance. Meanwhile, RF consumes most considerable time in both training and test time. Additionally, RF accuracy is also inferior to the other models.

The implications of these discoveries are substantial in diverse fields, especially in healthcare and well-being. The diverse input features introduced in the work are helpful not only for this research but also for other posture recognition with accelerations. Precise categorization of sleep postures can offer useful information for managing diseases such as obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), acid reflux, and musculoskeletal discomfort. Furthermore, it can assist athletes in maximizing their

recovery and performance, as well as provide insights for creating sleep environments that are ergonomically designed. Last but not least, this research highlights the capacity to combine MEMS accelerometers with ML algorithms to accurately classify sleep positions. Utilizing these technologies can enhance our comprehension of sleep patterns and postures, ultimately leading to enhanced health and well-being for individuals across various groups.

In the future, the system will be tested on more dataset in diverse population for extend validation. Moreover, more potential algorithms can be taken into account for further comparisons.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Matrella Guido: Visualization, Investigation. **Hoang Minh Long:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ciampolini Paolo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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